

Chain Position Optimization of a 4UPS–UPU Parallel Mechanism Considering Dynamic Coupling Effects

Abstract

The strong dynamic coupling effects among kinematic chains are not beneficial to the control of parallel mechanisms. This paper deals with the chain position optimization of a 4UPS–UPU parallel mechanism to reduce dynamic coupling effects among kinematic chains. Using the kinematic model, the Jacobian matrix is derived, and a method is proposed to transform it into a non-dimensional form and being independent of scaling factors. A singularity index is formulated based on the normalized determinant of the modified Jacobian matrix, guiding the optimization of chain positions at the base platform. Subsequently, the dynamic model is derived by using the principle of virtual work and a novel dynamic coupling index is proposed by taking both the inertia and centrifugal terms in the dynamic model into account. The neural network is then employed to enhance the calculation efficiency of the dynamic coupling index. Finally, the chain positions at the moving platform are optimized using Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm. This optimization process significantly reduces the dynamic coupling effects among kinematic chains in the parallel mechanism, thereby conferring advantageous benefits to its overall control.

Keywords

parallel mechanism, optimal design, kinematic chain, dynamic coupling

1 Introduction

Since the debut of the Gough-Stewart platform in the 1960s, parallel mechanisms have drawn great attention in both academic and industrial spheres. The most notable feature of parallel mechanisms is that the moving platform and fixed base are connected by multiple closed-loop chains. Furthermore, this multi-loop structure facilitates the arrangement of near-base-mounted actuation. These distinct characteristics impart some intrinsic advantages to parallel mechanisms compared with serial ones, including high stiffness¹⁻³, high compactness⁴ and high motion dynamics⁵. These merits pave the way for the widespread application of parallel mechanisms across the manufacturing and automation sectors. Notably, parallel mechanisms have extensive applications in developing various mechanical products, such as spray-painting robots^{6, 7}, flight simulators⁸, truss antennas⁹, minimal-invasive surgery devices¹⁰, vibration and earthquake simulators^{11, 12} and so on. However, parallel mechanisms are still far less popular in industrial applications compared with serial mechanisms. There are many reasons causing the delay of their application, with two prominent challenges being their strong singularity^{13, 14} and highly coupled dynamics^{15, 16}.

Singularity is a pivotal concern of parallel mechanisms. The assessment of singularity of parallel

mechanisms often relies on the Jacobian matrix. The Jacobian matrix signifies the velocity transformation between the base space and joint space, with its determinant being a crucial metric for evaluating singularity of parallel mechanisms. However, the determinant lacks a physical interpretation for parallel mechanisms with translational and rotational DOFs^{17, 18}. Two effective approaches to address the problem are to adopt a characteristic length to normalize the translational elements in the Jacobian matrix^{19, 20} or to use the map between joint velocity and linear velocity of designated points at the moving platform as the non-dimensional Jacobian matrix^{21, 22}. However, the former lacks physical meaning and the selection of the characteristic length is somewhat arbitrary, while the latter lacks universality and can be tedious.

Another pivotal concern of parallel mechanisms is the strong coupling effects among kinematic chains. It is crucial to quantitatively evaluate and minimize the coupling effects as much as possible²³. Ogbobe²⁴ analyzed the dynamic coupling effects of a Stewart manipulator by neglecting the centrifugal and gravity terms in the dynamic equation. Wang²⁵ evaluated the coupling characteristics of a 3-DOF parallel tool head by neglecting the centrifugal term. It's worth noting that the centrifugal term wields a significant influence on the dynamics. Consequently, the coupling indices derived from these studies cannot accurately reflect the coupling effects among kinematic chains of parallel mechanisms.

In this paper, a singularity index based on the modified Jacobian matrix, both non-dimensional and scaling irrelevant, is proposed. A novel dynamic coupling index which considers the centrifugal term in the dynamic model is also proposed. Based on these two indices, the chain positions at the base platform are optimized to reduce singularity while those at the moving platform are optimized to reduce dynamic coupling effects.

2 Kinematic analysis

2.1 Structure description

The schematic diagram of a 4UPS–UPU parallel mechanism is shown in Fig. 1. The moving platform is connected to the base by four UPS chains in the circumference and one UPU chain in the middle, where U, P and S represent the universal joint, prismatic joint and spherical joint, respectively. The two perpendicular axes of the U joint at each end of the UPU chain are parallel when the base and the moving platform are parallel to each other. The two perpendicular axes of the U joint at the UPS chain are in radial and circumferential directions.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of a 4UPS-UPU mechanism

The base coordinate system B_0-XYZ is placed at the base center with the X and Y axes being the rotation axes of the U joint at B_0 , respectively. The Z axis satisfies the right-hand rule. The body fixed coordinate system A_0-xyz is placed at the center of the moving platform with the x and y axes being the rotation axes of the U joint at A_0 , respectively. Establish the fixed coordinate system $B_i-x_iy_iz_i$ ($i = 0, \dots, 4$) with the x_i and y_i axes being the rotation axes of the U joint at B_i . Meanwhile, the body fixed coordinate system $B_i-u_iv_iw_i$ ($i = 0, \dots, 4$) is established, with the w_i axis being coincident with the axial direction of the i th chain and the u_i axis being coincident with the cross product of the y_i axis and w_i axis. B_i represents the center of the joint connecting the base and the i th chain, while A_i ($i = 0, \dots, 4$) represents the center of the joint connecting the moving platform and the i th chain. Both the base platform and the moving platform are circular, and their radius are R and r , respectively.

Denote the rotation angle of the U joint at the base end of the UPU chain around the Y axis as θ_1 and around the X axis as θ_2 , while at the moving platform the rotation angle around the x axis and y axis are denoted by θ_4 and θ_5 , respectively. Let the angle between B_0B_1 and the Y axis be θ_{B1} and the angle between B_0B_3 and the Y axis be θ_{B2} . Let the angle between A_0A_1 and the y axis be θ_{A1} and the angle between A_0A_3 and the y axis be θ_{A2} . Considering dynamic isotropy of the parallel mechanism, the hinge points B_1 and B_2 , B_3 and B_4 , A_1 and A_2 , A_3 and A_4 are symmetrically placed and θ_{B1} equals θ_{B2} .

For convenience, each telescopic chain A_iB_i ($i = 0, \dots, 4$) is divided into two components: (1) L_{Bi} (including the motor and the hollow tube) which undergoes a fixed-point rotation about B_i , with its center of mass denoted by CB_i and length denoted by l_{Bi} ; (2) L_{Ai} (including the screw nut and the rod stretching out to push the moving platform) which undergoes a compound motion of a fixed-point rotation about B_i and a sliding motion along the w_i axis, with its center of mass denoted by CA_i and length denoted by l_{Ai} .

2.2 Kinematic analysis

The orientation of A_0 - xyz with respect to B_0 - XYZ can be described as

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} c_1c_5 - s_1s_5c_{24} & -s_1s_{24} & c_1s_5 + s_1c_5c_{24} \\ -s_5s_{24} & c_{24} & c_5s_{24} \\ -s_1c_5 - c_1s_5c_{24} & -c_1s_{24} & -s_1s_5 + c_1c_5c_{24} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where s_1 , c_1 , s_{24} and c_{24} represent $\sin\theta_1$, $\cos\theta_1$, $\sin(\theta_2 + \theta_4)$ and $\cos(\theta_2 + \theta_4)$, respectively.

The position vector of A_0 with respect to B_0 - XYZ can be described as $\mathbf{r} = [x \ y \ z]^T$, in which x and z are coupled with the relation

$$x = zt_1 \quad (2)$$

where t_1 represents $\tan\theta_1$. By Eq. (1) and Eq. (2), the 5 DOFs of the mechanism can be expressed by $\mathbf{P} = [y \ z \ \theta_1 \ \theta_{24} \ \theta_5]^T$. Here, θ_1 instead of x is chosen to simplify later derivation. For convenience, y , z , θ_1 , θ_{24} and θ_5 are denoted by P_1 , P_2 , P_3 , P_4 and P_5 , respectively.

The closed-loop constraint equation associated with the i th chain can be written as

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{b}_i + q_i \mathbf{w}_i - \mathbf{a}_i, \quad i = 0, \dots, 4 \quad (3)$$

where q_i and \mathbf{w}_i are the length and the unit vector of the i th chain; \mathbf{a}_i and \mathbf{b}_i are position vectors of A_i and B_i ; $\mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{R}\mathbf{a}'_i$ and \mathbf{a}'_i denotes the position vector of A_i in A_0 - xyz . Based on Eq. (3), the length and orientation of the i th chain can be expressed as

$$q_i = \|\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{a}_i - \mathbf{b}_i\|_2, \quad \mathbf{w}_i = \frac{\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{a}_i - \mathbf{b}_i}{q_i} \quad (4)$$

Taking the derivative of \mathbf{r} yields

$$\dot{\mathbf{r}} = \mathbf{J}_v \dot{\mathbf{P}} \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_v = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & t_1 & z(1+t_1^2) & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$. Denote the angular velocity of the moving platform as

$\boldsymbol{\omega} = [\omega_x \ \omega_y \ \omega_z]^T$, which can be expressed by

$$[\boldsymbol{\omega} \times] = \dot{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{R}^T \quad (6)$$

where $[\boldsymbol{\omega} \times] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\omega_z & \omega_y \\ \omega_z & 0 & -\omega_x \\ -\omega_y & \omega_x & 0 \end{bmatrix}$. Equation (6) can be rewritten as

$$\boldsymbol{\omega} = \mathbf{J}_\omega \dot{\mathbf{P}} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_\omega = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -c_1 & -s_1s_{24} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & c_{24} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & s_1 & -c_1s_{24} \end{bmatrix}$.

Taking the time derivative of Eq. (3) yields

$$\dot{\mathbf{r}} = \dot{q}_i \mathbf{w}_i + q_i \boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times \mathbf{w}_i - \boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{a}_i \quad (8)$$

where \dot{q}_i and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_i$ are the actuated joint rate and the angular velocity of the i th chain. Taking the dot product with \mathbf{w}_i on both side of Eq. (8) leads to

$$\dot{q}_i = \mathbf{w}_i^T (\dot{\mathbf{r}} + \boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{a}_i) \quad (9)$$

Equation (9) can be rewritten as

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{J} \dot{\mathbf{P}} \quad (10)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{q}} = [\dot{q}_0 \ \cdots \ \dot{q}_4]^T$ and $\mathbf{J} = \left[(\mathbf{J}_v - [\mathbf{a}_0 \times] \mathbf{J}_\omega)^T \mathbf{w}_0 \ \cdots \ (\mathbf{J}_v - [\mathbf{a}_4 \times] \mathbf{J}_\omega)^T \mathbf{w}_4 \right]^T$.

Let φ_i and η_i be the rotation angle about the two axes of U joints of the i th chain and γ_i be the angle from the y_i axis to the Y axis in the clockwise direction. Therefore, the rotation matrix from B_0 -XYZ to B_i - $u_i v_i w_i$ can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{R}_i = \text{Rot}(Z, -\gamma_i) \text{Rot}(y_i, \varphi_i) \text{Rot}(u_i, \eta_i) = \begin{bmatrix} c\gamma_i c\varphi_i & s\gamma_i c\eta_i + c\gamma_i s\varphi_i s\eta_i & -s\gamma_i s\eta_i + c\gamma_i s\varphi_i c\eta_i \\ -c\gamma_i s\varphi_i & c\gamma_i c\eta_i + s\gamma_i s\varphi_i s\eta_i & c\gamma_i s\eta_i - s\gamma_i s\varphi_i c\eta_i \\ -s\varphi_i & c\varphi_i s\eta_i & c\varphi_i c\eta_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Let $\mathbf{w}_i = [w_{ix} \ w_{iy} \ w_{iz}]^T$. Equation (11) indicates that

$$\mathbf{w}_i = \mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{e}_3 = [-s\gamma_i s\eta_i + c\gamma_i s\varphi_i c\eta_i \quad c\gamma_i s\eta_i - s\gamma_i s\varphi_i c\eta_i \quad c\varphi_i c\eta_i]^T \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{e}_j is a unit column vector with the j th element being one. Thus, φ_i and η_i can be written as

$$\begin{cases} \varphi_i = \arctan \frac{w_{ix} c\gamma_i - w_{iy} s\gamma_i}{w_{iz}} \\ \eta_i = \arcsin (w_{ix} s\gamma_i + w_{iy} c\gamma_i) \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Differentiating Eq. (4) leads to

$$\dot{\mathbf{w}}_i = \mathbf{J}_{wi} \dot{\mathbf{P}} \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_{wi} = (\mathbf{J}_v - [\mathbf{a}_i \times] \mathbf{J}_\omega) (\mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{w}_i \mathbf{w}_i^T) / q_i$; \mathbf{I}_3 is an identity matrix of three rows. Taking the time derivative of Eq. (13) yields

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\varphi}_i = \frac{1}{\kappa_i} [w_{iz} c\gamma_i \quad -w_{iz} s\gamma_i \quad w_{iy} s\gamma_i - w_{ix} c\gamma_i] \dot{\mathbf{w}}_i \\ \dot{\eta}_i = -\frac{1}{\lambda_i} [s\gamma_i \quad c\gamma_i \quad 0] \dot{\mathbf{w}}_i \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where $\kappa_i = (w_{ix} c\gamma_i - w_{iy} s\gamma_i)^2 + w_{iz}^2$ and $\lambda_i = \sqrt{1 - (w_{ix} s\gamma_i + w_{iy} c\gamma_i)^2}$. Taking the same procedure on \mathbf{R}_i as Eq. (9) leads to the angular velocity of the i th chain

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}_i = \mathbf{J}_{\omega i} \dot{\mathbf{P}} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{J}_{oi} = \left\{ \frac{1}{\kappa_i} \begin{bmatrix} w_{iz} s \gamma_i c \gamma_i & -w_{iz} s^2 \gamma_i & (w_{iy} s \gamma_i - w_{ix} c \gamma_i) s \gamma_i \\ w_{iz} c^2 \gamma_i & -w_{iz} s \gamma_i c \gamma_i & (w_{iy} s \gamma_i - w_{ix} c \gamma_i) c \gamma_i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{\lambda_i} \begin{bmatrix} s \gamma_i c \gamma_i c \varphi_i & c^2 \gamma_i c \varphi_i & 0 \\ -s^2 \gamma_i c \varphi_i & -s \gamma_i c \gamma_i c \varphi_i & 0 \\ -s \gamma_i s \varphi_i & -c \gamma_i s \varphi_i & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \mathbf{J}_{wi}.$$

Let the length from B_i to CB_i and CA_i be r_{Bi} and r_{Ai} , respectively. The linear velocity of the lower and upper part of the i th chain can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{Bi} = r_{Bi} \boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times \mathbf{w}_i = \mathbf{J}_{vBi} \dot{\mathbf{P}} \\ \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{Ai} = r_{Ai} \boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times \mathbf{w}_i + \dot{q}_i \mathbf{w}_i = \mathbf{J}_{vAi} \dot{\mathbf{P}} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_{vBi} = -r_{Bi} [\mathbf{w}_i \times] \mathbf{J}_{oi}$ and $\mathbf{J}_{vAi} = -r_{Ai} [\mathbf{w}_i \times] \mathbf{J}_{oi} + \mathbf{w}_i \mathbf{e}_i^T \mathbf{J}$.

2.3 Modification of Jacobian matrix

The dimensions of the Jacobian matrix for robots with translational and rotational DOFs are inhomogeneous. Here, a method is proposed to unify the dimensions of the Jacobian matrix based on the moving range of P_i ($i = 1, \dots, 5$) and q_i ($i = 0, \dots, 4$). The method includes the following three steps.

Step 1. Solve for the maximum moving range of P_i and q_i , denoted by d_i and b_i , respectively.

Step 2. Divide the Cartesian coordinate P_i by its corresponding maximum moving range. It leads to the non-dimensional velocity $\hat{\mathbf{P}}$, which is the ratio between the moving distance of P_i during unit time when P_i moves at the velocity of \dot{P}_i and d_i .

Step 3. Repeat Step 2 on \dot{q} .

Applying the above procedure yields

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{P}} = \mathbf{D} \hat{\mathbf{P}} \\ \dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{B} \hat{\mathbf{q}} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}(d_1 \ \dots \ d_5)$, $\hat{\mathbf{P}} = [\hat{P}_1 \ \dots \ \hat{P}_5]^T$, $\mathbf{B} = \text{diag}(b_0 \ \dots \ b_4)$, $\hat{\mathbf{q}} = [\hat{q}_0 \ \dots \ \hat{q}_4]^T$.

Therefore, the mapping from $\hat{\mathbf{P}}$ to $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ can be expressed as

$$\hat{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{J}_{re} \hat{\mathbf{P}} \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_{re} = \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{J} \mathbf{D}$ is the modified Jacobian matrix. \mathbf{J}_{re} unifies the dimensions of linear and angular motion and has a clear physical meaning. The determinant of \mathbf{J}_{re} can be written as

$$\det \mathbf{J}_{re} = k \det \mathbf{J} \quad (20)$$

where $k = \prod_{i=1}^5 d_i / b_{i-1}$ is the modification coefficient of the determinant. The distribution of k is shown

in Fig. 2 with θ_{B1} (θ_{B2}) varying from 5° to 45° . It can be seen that the value of k varies significantly with different θ_{B1} (θ_{B2}), θ_{A1} and θ_{A2} , which shows the necessity to make such a modification.

Fig. 2 Modification coefficient

In addition to its non-dimensional characteristics, it's important to note that the determinant of the modified Jacobian matrix is scaling independent. In general, the determinants of the traditional Jacobian matrix for the original parallel mechanism and its scaled one under the same configuration are different. Thus, it is not reasonable to compare their singularity by using the determinants of the traditional Jacobian matrix. However, the determinants of the modified Jacobian matrix for the original mechanism and its scaled one are the same. It is validated by comparing the original mechanism with a scaled one, whose chain length and platform radius are five times longer, as shown in Fig. 3. The determinants of the modified Jacobian matrix are calculated in a spherical workspace with the center being $\mathbf{P}_0 = [(q_{0\min} + q_{0\max})/2 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T$.

Fig. 3 Determinants of the modified Jacobian matrix

Fig. 3 shows that the determinants of the modified Jacobian matrix for the original mechanism

and its scaled one are the same. Therefore, the determinant of the modified Jacobian matrix offers a good way to measure singularity.

Given that the modified matrix \mathbf{J}_{re} effectively addresses the inhomogeneity problem arising from variations in translational and rotational velocity units, its determinant can be used to investigate the singularity of a parallel mechanism featuring mixed DOFs. A determinant value approaching 0 or infinity indicates the mechanism's proximity to a singular configuration. Additionally, the reciprocity of the determinants implies that the velocity transmission characteristics are identical in magnitude but opposite in direction. Thus, a new singularity index (SI) can be defined as

$$\text{SI} = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{1}{k|\det \mathbf{J}|} & |\det \mathbf{J}| \geq \frac{1}{k} \\ 1 - k|\det \mathbf{J}| & |\det \mathbf{J}| < \frac{1}{k} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

Equation (21) shows that a large SI corresponds to strong singularity. In order to validate this relationship, SI of the mechanism when $\theta_{B1} = \theta_{B2} = \theta_{A1} = \theta_{A2} = 45^\circ$ is calculated within a cube centered at \mathbf{P}_0 , as shown in Fig. 4. When $\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{P}_0$, the moving platform exhibits rotational freedom around x axis or y axis despite constant chain lengths. It constitutes a singular scenario, as corroborated by SI in Fig. 4. Thus, the singularity index SI is effective in judging singularity of mechanisms with same structures regardless of their scaling.

Fig. 4 SI of the mechanism with highly singular configuration

The proposed method makes the Jacobian matrix non-dimensional and eliminates the scaling effect on the Jacobian matrix, which enables SI to signify singularity of a mechanism. Due to the advantage of the proposed method, SI can also be adopted as a universal tool to judge singularity of other non-redundant parallel mechanisms.

2.4 Chain position optimization at the base platform

The chain positions at the base platform are optimized to avoid singularity as much as possible.

The initial position \mathbf{P}_0 is taken as the reference to evaluate singularity of specified chain positions because it locates at the same place whatever the chain positions are, which make $SI(\mathbf{P}_0)$ well implies the singular characteristics of the mechanism. $SI(\mathbf{P}_0)$ correlates to the chain positions not only at the base but also at the moving platform. Therefore, a mean singularity index (MSI) is defined to cover different chain positions at the moving platform

$$MSI = \frac{\int_{\theta_{A1}=0}^{\pi/2} \int_{\theta_{A2}=0}^{\pi/2} SI(\mathbf{P}_0, \theta_{A1}, \theta_{A2}, \theta_{B1}, \theta_{B1}) d\theta_{A1} d\theta_{A2}}{\int_{\theta_{A1}=0}^{\pi/2} \int_{\theta_{A2}=0}^{\pi/2} d\theta_{A1} d\theta_{A2}} \quad (22)$$

Based on Eq. (22), MSI at \mathbf{P}_0 for varying values of θ_{B1} (θ_{B2}) is calculated, as depicted in Fig. 5. The geometric parameters of the 5-DOF parallel mechanism can be found in Appendix A.1. Notably, l_{Bi} and l_{Ai} ($i = 1, \dots, 4$) depend on four parameters subject to optimization, i.e., θ_{B1} , θ_{B2} , θ_{A1} and θ_{A2} . Each telescopic link $A_i B_i$ ($i = 0, \dots, 4$) operates within the range of $[l_{Bi}, l_{Bi} + l_{Ai}]$.

It's clear that MSI reaches minimum at θ_{B1} (θ_{B2}) = 45° , which is then chosen as the optimized parameters of the chain positions at the base platform. In such a configuration, the parallel mechanism is far from singularity.

Fig. 5 MSI at \mathbf{P}_0 of different θ_{B1} (θ_{B2})

3 Dynamic model of the parallel mechanism

3.1 Acceleration analysis

By taking the time derivative of Eq. (5) and Eq. (7), the linear and angular acceleration of the moving platform can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases} \ddot{\mathbf{r}} = \mathbf{J}_v \ddot{\mathbf{P}} + \dot{\mathbf{J}}_v \dot{\mathbf{P}} \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} = \mathbf{J}_\omega \ddot{\mathbf{P}} + \dot{\mathbf{J}}_\omega \dot{\mathbf{P}} \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{J}_v = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \dot{\theta}_i / c_1^2 & (1 + t_1^2) \dot{z} + 2z t_1 \dot{\theta}_i / c_1^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } \mathbf{J}_\omega = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & s_1 \dot{\theta}_1 & -c_1 s_{24} \dot{\theta}_1 - s_1 c_{24} \dot{\theta}_{24} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -s_{24} \dot{\theta}_{24} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c_1 \dot{\theta}_1 & s_1 s_{24} \dot{\theta}_1 - c_1 c_{24} \dot{\theta}_{24} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Taking the time derivative of Eq. (9) yields

$$\ddot{q}_i = \mathbf{w}_i^T \left(\ddot{\mathbf{r}} - \dot{q}_i [\boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times] [\boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times] \mathbf{w}_i + \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \times \mathbf{a}_i + [\boldsymbol{\omega} \times] [\boldsymbol{\omega} \times] \mathbf{a}_i \right) \quad (24)$$

Equation (24) can be rewritten as

$$\ddot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{J}\ddot{\mathbf{P}} + \dot{\mathbf{J}}\dot{\mathbf{P}} \quad (25)$$

$$\text{where } \dot{\mathbf{J}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{w}_0^T \left(\dot{\mathbf{J}}_v + q_0 [\boldsymbol{\omega}_0 \times] [\boldsymbol{\omega}_0 \times] \mathbf{J}_{\omega 0} - [\mathbf{a}_0 \times] \dot{\mathbf{J}}_\omega - [\boldsymbol{\omega} \times] [\mathbf{a}_0 \times] \mathbf{J}_\omega \right) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{w}_4^T \left(\dot{\mathbf{J}}_v + q_4 [\boldsymbol{\omega}_4 \times] [\boldsymbol{\omega}_4 \times] \mathbf{J}_{\omega 4} - [\mathbf{a}_4 \times] \dot{\mathbf{J}}_\omega - [\boldsymbol{\omega} \times] [\mathbf{a}_4 \times] \mathbf{J}_\omega \right) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Differentiating Eq. (14) with respect to time leads to

$$\dot{\mathbf{w}}_i = \mathbf{J}_{wi} \ddot{\mathbf{P}} + \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{wi} \dot{\mathbf{P}} \quad (26)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{J}}_{wi} = \left[\left(\dot{\mathbf{J}}_v - [(\boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{a}_i) \times] \mathbf{J}_\omega - [\mathbf{a}_i \times] \dot{\mathbf{J}}_\omega \right) (\mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{w}_i \mathbf{w}_i^T) - (\mathbf{J}_v - [\mathbf{a}_i \times] \mathbf{J}_\omega) (\dot{\mathbf{w}}_i \mathbf{w}_i^T + \mathbf{w}_i \dot{\mathbf{w}}_i^T) - \dot{q}_i \mathbf{J}_{wi} \right] / q_i$. Taking the time derivative of Eq. (16) leads to

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_i = \mathbf{J}_{oi} \ddot{\mathbf{P}} + \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{oi} \dot{\mathbf{P}} \quad (27)$$

The expression of $\dot{\mathbf{J}}_{oi}$ is show in Appendix A.2.

Differentiating Eq. (17) with respect to time leads to

$$\begin{cases} \ddot{\mathbf{r}}_{Bi} = r_{Bi} \left(\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_i \times \mathbf{w}_i + [\boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times] [\boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times] \mathbf{w}_i \right) = \mathbf{J}_{vBi} \ddot{\mathbf{P}} + \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{vBi} \dot{\mathbf{P}} \\ \ddot{\mathbf{r}}_{Ai} = r_{Ai} \left(\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_i \times \mathbf{w}_i + [\boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times] [\boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times] \mathbf{w}_i \right) + \ddot{q}_i \mathbf{w}_i + \dot{q}_i \boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times \mathbf{w}_i = \mathbf{J}_{vAi} \ddot{\mathbf{P}} + \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{vAi} \dot{\mathbf{P}} \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

where

$$\dot{\mathbf{J}}_{vBi} = \left\{ \left(\boldsymbol{\omega}_i^T \mathbf{w}_i \mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{w}_i \boldsymbol{\omega}_i^T \right) \mathbf{J}_{oi} - [\mathbf{w}_i \times] \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{oi} \right\} r_{Bi} \quad \text{and}$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{J}}_{vAi} = \left\{ \left(\boldsymbol{\omega}_i^T \mathbf{w}_i \mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{w}_i \boldsymbol{\omega}_i^T \right) \mathbf{J}_{oi} - [\mathbf{w}_i \times] \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{oi} \right\} r_{Ai} + \mathbf{w}_i \mathbf{e}_i^T \dot{\mathbf{J}} - \dot{q}_i [\mathbf{w}_i \times] \mathbf{J}_{oi}.$$

3.2 Dynamic modeling

The resultant of gravity and inertia force and moment imposed on the moving platform can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{F}_A = \begin{bmatrix} m_A \mathbf{g} - m_A \ddot{\mathbf{r}} \\ -\mathbf{I}_A \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} - [\boldsymbol{\omega}_A \times] \mathbf{I}_A \boldsymbol{\omega}_A \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

where m_A is the mass of the moving platform, \mathbf{I}_A is its moment of inertia in B_0 -XYZ and \mathbf{g} is the gravitational acceleration. The forces and moments imposing on each component of the i th chain can be written as

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{F}_{Bi} = \begin{bmatrix} m_{Bi} \mathbf{g} - m_{Bi} \ddot{\mathbf{r}}_{Bi} \\ -\mathbf{I}_{Bi} \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_i - [\boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times] \mathbf{I}_{Bi} \boldsymbol{\omega}_i \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{F}_{Ai} = \begin{bmatrix} m_{Ai} \mathbf{g} - m_{Ai} \ddot{\mathbf{r}}_{Ai} \\ -\mathbf{I}_{Ai} \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_i - [\boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times] \mathbf{I}_{Ai} \boldsymbol{\omega}_i \end{bmatrix} \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

where m_{Bi} and m_{Ai} are the mass of two parts of the telescopic chain $A_i B_i$, \mathbf{I}_{Bi} and \mathbf{I}_{Ai} are their moment of inertia in B_0 -XYZ. The virtual work principles states

$$\delta \mathbf{q}^T \boldsymbol{\tau} + \delta \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{F}_A + \sum_{i=0}^4 \delta \mathbf{x}_{Bi}^T \mathbf{F}_{Bi} + \sum_{i=0}^4 \delta \mathbf{x}_{Ai}^T \mathbf{F}_{Ai} = \mathbf{0} \quad (31)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ represents the actuated force. The inertia parameters of the 5-DOF parallel mechanism are provided in Appendix A.1. Notably, the ' superscript following \mathbf{I} indicates that the component's moment of inertia is measured in its own coordinate system.

Substituting the variation relationships $\delta \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{J} \delta \mathbf{P}$, $\delta \mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{J}_v^T \quad \mathbf{J}_\omega^T]^T \delta \mathbf{P}$, $\delta \mathbf{x}_{Bi}^T = [\mathbf{J}_{vBi}^T \quad \mathbf{J}_{\omega i}^T]^T \delta \mathbf{P}$, $\delta \mathbf{x}_{Ai}^T = [\mathbf{J}_{vAi}^T \quad \mathbf{J}_{\omega i}^T]^T \delta \mathbf{P}$ into Eq. (31) results in the dynamic equation

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \boldsymbol{\tau}_a + \boldsymbol{\tau}_v + \boldsymbol{\tau}_G \quad (32)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\tau}_a$, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_v$ and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_G$ are the inertia term, centrifugal term and gravitational term, respectively. These three terms can be further expressed as

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_a = \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{P}) \ddot{\mathbf{P}}, \quad \boldsymbol{\tau}_v = \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{P}, \dot{\mathbf{P}}), \quad \boldsymbol{\tau}_G = \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{P}) \quad (33)$$

where

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{J}^{-T} \left\{ m_A \mathbf{J}_v^T \mathbf{J}_v + \mathbf{J}_\omega^T \mathbf{I}_A \mathbf{J}_\omega + \sum_{i=0}^4 \left[m_{Bi} \mathbf{J}_{vBi}^T \mathbf{J}_{vBi} + \mathbf{J}_{\omega i}^T (\mathbf{I}_{Bi} + \mathbf{I}_{Ai}) \mathbf{J}_{\omega i} + m_{Ai} \mathbf{J}_{vAi}^T \mathbf{J}_{vAi} \right] \right\},$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{J}^{-T} \left(m_A \mathbf{J}_v^T \dot{\mathbf{J}}_v + \mathbf{J}_\omega^T \mathbf{I}_A \dot{\mathbf{J}}_\omega + \mathbf{J}_\omega^T \left[(\mathbf{J}_\omega \dot{\mathbf{P}}) \times \right] \mathbf{I}_A \mathbf{J}_\omega + \sum_{i=0}^4 \left\{ m_{Bi} \mathbf{J}_{vBi}^T \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{vBi} + \mathbf{J}_{\omega i}^T (\mathbf{I}_{Bi} + \mathbf{I}_{Ai}) \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{\omega i} + \mathbf{J}_{\omega i}^T \left[(\mathbf{J}_{\omega i} \dot{\mathbf{P}}) \times \right] (\mathbf{I}_{Bi} + \mathbf{I}_{Ai}) \mathbf{J}_{\omega i} + m_{Ai} \mathbf{J}_{vAi}^T \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{vAi} \right\} \right) \dot{\mathbf{P}}, \quad \text{and}$$

$$\mathbf{G} = -\mathbf{J}^{-T} \left[m_A \mathbf{J}_v^T + \sum_{i=0}^4 (m_{Bi} \mathbf{J}_{vBi}^T + m_{Ai} \mathbf{J}_{vAi}^T) \right] \mathbf{g}.$$

The centrifugal term of the i th chain C_i can be expressed in a quadratic form as

$$C_i = \dot{\mathbf{P}}^T \mathbf{H}_i(\mathbf{P}) \dot{\mathbf{P}} \quad (34)$$

The derivation of Eq. (34) is shown in Appendix A.3.

Therefore, Eq. (32) can be rewritten as

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_i = \mathbf{e}_i^T \mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{P}} + \dot{\mathbf{P}}^T \mathbf{H}_i \dot{\mathbf{P}} + \mathbf{e}_i^T \mathbf{G} \quad (35)$$

Equation (35) is the dynamic equation in the base space, which should be rewritten in the joint space for further consideration of coupling effects. Combining Eq. (25) and Eq. (35) yields

$$\begin{cases} \tau_{ai} = \mathbf{e}_i^T \mathbf{M} \mathbf{J}^{-1} \ddot{\mathbf{q}} \\ \tau_{vi} = \dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{J}^{-T} \mathbf{H}_i \mathbf{J}^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{q}} - \mathbf{e}_i^T \mathbf{M} \mathbf{J}^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} \dot{\tilde{\mathbf{q}}} \tilde{\mathbf{J}} \mathbf{J}^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{q}} \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} = [\tilde{\mathbf{J}}_1^{-1} \quad \dots \quad \tilde{\mathbf{J}}_5^{-1}]$, $\dot{\tilde{\mathbf{q}}} = \text{diag}(\dot{q}_1 \quad \dots \quad \dot{q}_5)$ (there are 25 \dot{q} s in total) and

$$\dot{\tilde{\mathbf{J}}} = \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{J}^T}{\partial \dot{P}_1} \quad \dots \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{J}^T}{\partial \dot{P}_5} \right]^T; \quad \tilde{\mathbf{J}}_j^{-1} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{e}_j^T \mathbf{J}^{-1} \quad \mathbf{e}_j^T \mathbf{J}^{-1} \quad \mathbf{e}_j^T \mathbf{J}^{-1} \quad \mathbf{e}_j^T \mathbf{J}^{-1} \quad \mathbf{e}_j^T \mathbf{J}^{-1}),$$

Thus, Eq. (36) can be written as

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\tau}}{\partial \dot{P}_j} = \left[\frac{\partial (\mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{e}_1)}{\partial \dot{P}_j} \quad \dots \quad \frac{\partial (\mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{e}_5)}{\partial \dot{P}_j} \right]^T$$

$$\tau_{ai} = \mathbf{e}_i^T \tilde{\mathbf{M}} \ddot{\mathbf{q}}, \quad \tau_{vi} = \dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_i \dot{\mathbf{q}} \quad (37)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{M}} = \mathbf{M} \mathbf{J}^{-1}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_i = \mathbf{J}^{-T} \mathbf{H}_i \mathbf{J}^{-1} - \hat{\mathbf{H}}_i$;

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{i(m,j)} = \sum_{k=1}^{5^2} \left[\left(\sum_{r=1}^5 \sum_{s=1}^5 \mathbf{e}_i^T \mathbf{M} \mathbf{e}_s \mathbf{e}_s^T \mathbf{J}^{-1} \mathbf{e}_r \mathbf{e}_r^T \tilde{\mathbf{J}}^{-1} \mathbf{e}_{j+5k-5} \right) \left(\sum_{s=1}^5 \mathbf{e}_i^T \tilde{\mathbf{J}} \mathbf{e}_s \mathbf{e}_s^T \mathbf{J}^{-1} \mathbf{e}_m \right) \right].$$

4 Dynamic coupling index

4.1 Dynamic coupling index of each chain

An important method to judge the coupling effects is to determine the source of the chain's actuating force. If it originates from the chain's own movement, there won't be coupling effects. However, if the force results from the movement of other chains, coupling occurs. Consequently, the inertia term is divided into a non-coupling term τ_{ai_nc} and a coupling term τ_{ai_c} , as well as the centrifugal term. By separating the non-coupling and coupling terms, it leads to

$$\begin{cases} \tau_{ai_nc} = \left| \mathbf{e}_i^T \tilde{\mathbf{M}} \mathbf{e}_i \ddot{\mathbf{q}}_i \right|, & \tau_{ai_c} = \left| \mathbf{e}_i^T \tilde{\mathbf{M}} \ddot{\mathbf{q}} \right| - \left| \mathbf{e}_i^T \tilde{\mathbf{M}} \mathbf{e}_i \ddot{\mathbf{q}}_i \right| \\ \tau_{vi_nc} = \left| \mathbf{e}_i^T \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_i \mathbf{e}_i \dot{\mathbf{q}}_i^2 \right|, & \tau_{vi_c} = \left| \dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_i \dot{\mathbf{q}} \right| - \left| \mathbf{e}_i^T \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_i \mathbf{e}_i \dot{\mathbf{q}}_i^2 \right| \end{cases} \quad (38)$$

The dynamic coupling index (DCI) of the i th chain is defined as

$$\text{DCI}_i = \left(\tau_{ai_c} + \tau_{vi_c} \right) / \left(\tau_{ai_c} + \tau_{ai_nc} + \tau_{vi_c} + \tau_{vi_nc} \right) \quad (39)$$

Equation (39) shows that DCI correlates not only to the chain length but also the first and second order derivatives. Therefore, the local dynamic coupling index (LDCI) of the i th chain, which quantifies the coupling characteristics at a certain place, is defined as

$$\text{LDCI}_i = \int \cdots \int \int \cdots \int \text{DCI}_i d\dot{q}_1 \cdots d\dot{q}_n d\ddot{q}_1 \cdots d\ddot{q}_n / \int \cdots \int \int \cdots \int d\dot{q}_1 \cdots d\dot{q}_n d\ddot{q}_1 \cdots d\ddot{q}_n \quad (40)$$

Equation (40) shows that LDCI includes all possible velocity and acceleration at a specific pose and orientation in space. A small value of LDCI corresponds to weak dynamic coupling effects of a chain, which is desirable. However, multiple integration is included in Eq. (40), which makes it extremely tedious in calculation. Thus, it must be simplified with reasonable accuracy and acceptable calculation time.

In order to simplify Eq. (40), the property of Eq. (39) is investigated. When $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ scales from $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ to $\beta \hat{\mathbf{q}}$ with β ($\beta \neq 0$) being the scaling factor and $\ddot{\mathbf{q}}$ scales from $\hat{\ddot{\mathbf{q}}}$ to $\alpha \hat{\ddot{\mathbf{q}}}$ with α ($\alpha \neq 0$) being the scaling factor, Eq. (39) becomes

$$\text{DCI}_i = \left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta^2} \hat{\tau}_{ai_c} + \hat{\tau}_{vi_c} \right) / \left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta^2} \hat{\tau}_{ai} + \hat{\tau}_{vi} \right) \quad (41)$$

where $\hat{\tau}_{vi_nc}$, $\hat{\tau}_{vi_c}$, $\hat{\tau}_{ai_nc}$ and $\hat{\tau}_{ai_c}$ are evaluated under $\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ and $\hat{\ddot{\mathbf{q}}}$, $\hat{\tau}_{vi} = \hat{\tau}_{vi_c} + \hat{\tau}_{vi_nc}$ and $\hat{\tau}_{ai} = \hat{\tau}_{ai_c} + \hat{\tau}_{ai_nc}$. Equation (41) shows that DCI is relevant to the ratio between α and β^2 but not their

specific values when $\dot{\hat{q}}$ and $\ddot{\hat{q}}$ are constant. Therefore, $\|\dot{\hat{q}}\|_\infty = 1$ and $\|\ddot{\hat{q}}\|_\infty = 1$ are taken as the benchmark to calculate DCI at different velocity and acceleration. Different combinations of velocity and acceleration can be obtained by taking different ratios between α and β^2 as follows

$$\begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta^2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \frac{i}{m} \end{bmatrix}^T, i = 0, \dots, m & \alpha \geq \beta \\ \begin{bmatrix} \frac{i-m-1}{m} & 1 \end{bmatrix}^T, i = m+1, \dots, 2m & \beta > \alpha \end{cases} \quad m \rightarrow \infty \quad (42)$$

In this way, DCI at q of $(2m+1)$ different combinations of \dot{q} and \ddot{q} can be obtained by only calculating the four elements in Eq. (38) once, and the calculation efficiency is significantly increased.

It is assumed that $-\dot{q}_{i\max} < \dot{q}_i < \dot{q}_{i\max}$ and $-\ddot{q}_{i\max} < \ddot{q}_i < \ddot{q}_{i\max}$, $i = 0, \dots, 4$. It's worth noting that $\dot{q}_{i\max}$ and $\ddot{q}_{i\max}$ are not necessarily the same for different chains, which makes the area bounded by the motion capacity of the motors a 10-dimensional hyperrectangle instead of a hypercube. Therefore, if the elements of the summation sequence are evenly selected in the hypercubic area bounded by $\|\dot{\hat{q}}\|_\infty = 1$ and $\|\ddot{\hat{q}}\|_\infty = 1$, after they are scaled to the hyperrectangle bounded by $-\dot{q}_{i\max} < \dot{q}_i < \dot{q}_{i\max}$ and $-\ddot{q}_{i\max} < \ddot{q}_i < \ddot{q}_{i\max}$, these elements won't be evenly distributed. Therefore, the elements of the summation sequence shouldn't be chosen evenly without considering the motion capacity of each chain. In order to make the elements evenly distributed after mapping back to the hyperrectangle, the ratio among $\dot{q}_{0\max}, \dots, \dot{q}_{4\max}, \ddot{q}_{0\max}, \dots, \ddot{q}_{4\max}$ is approximated by $k_{\dot{q}_0} : \dots : k_{\dot{q}_4} : k_{\ddot{q}_0} : \dots : k_{\ddot{q}_4}$, where $k_{\dot{q}_i}$ and $k_{\ddot{q}_i}$ are positive integrals. \dot{q}_i is evenly divided into $sk_{\dot{q}_i}$ segments, while \ddot{q}_i is evenly divided into $sk_{\ddot{q}_i}$ segments between -1 and 1 , where s is a positive integral. Therefore, the multiple integration can be converted to summation

$$\text{LDCI}_i = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{\dot{q}_0} \dots \sum_{\dot{q}_4} \sum_{\ddot{q}_0} \dots \sum_{\ddot{q}_4} \sum_{\begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta^2 \end{bmatrix}} \frac{\alpha \hat{\tau}_{ai_nc} + \beta^2 \hat{\tau}_{vi_nc}}{\alpha \hat{\tau}_{ai} + \beta^2 \hat{\tau}_{vi}} \bigg/ (2m+1) \prod_{i=0}^4 (sk_{\dot{q}_i} + 1)(sk_{\ddot{q}_i} + 1) \quad (43)$$

Based on LDCI, a global dynamic coupling index (GDGI) in the workspace V_{ws} can be defined as

$$\text{GDGI}_i = \int_{V_{ws}} \text{LDCI}_i dV_{ws} \bigg/ \int_{V_{ws}} dV_{ws} \quad (44)$$

4.2 Dynamic coupling index of the parallel mechanism

Since GDGI reflects the dynamic coupling effects on a certain chain, it is a local evaluation index. Here, a comprehensive dynamic coupling index (CDCI) to consider the mechanism as a whole is proposed

$$\text{CDCI} = \sum_{i=0}^4 \frac{\text{GDCI}_i - \min(\text{GDCI}_i)}{\min(\text{GDCI}_i)} \quad (45)$$

where $\min(\text{GDCI}_i)$ represents the minimum GDCI of the i th chain with different θ_{A1} and θ_{A2} , which is also the best value. For each chain, the relative change of GDCI and its best is calculated, which is then summed together. CDCI not only reflects the difference between the dynamic coupling effect of each chain and its possible minimum, but also unifies five global dynamic coupling indices into one comprehensive dynamic coupling index, which brings convenience to the following optimization. The smaller CDCI is, the weaker dynamic coupling effects are.

The definition of CDCI is irrelevant to the configuration of the mechanism, and its calculation only requires a dynamic model in the form of Eq. (37). Therefore, it's applicable to other parallel mechanisms.

5 Chain position optimization based on dynamic coupling effects

5.1 Restraints of hinge point positions at the moving platform

To avoid singularity, some restraints of the hinge point positions at the moving platform must be specified. $\text{SI}(\mathbf{P}_0)$ defined in 2.3 is used to judge singularity of the mechanism, whose value shouldn't be too large. Besides, two kinematic pairs can't be too close in order to avoid interference with each other. Considering the symmetry of the mechanism, the constraints are given as

$$\begin{cases} \text{SI}(\mathbf{P}_0) < \text{SI}_{\text{th}} \\ \Delta\theta_{\min} \leq \theta_{A2} \leq \theta_{A1} \leq \frac{\pi}{2} \end{cases} \quad (46)$$

where SI_{th} is the threshold of SI and $\Delta\theta_{\min}$ is the minimum spacing between two joints. The area of θ_{A1} and θ_{A2} bounded by Eq. (46) is irregular. For the convenience of further optimization, it is expanded into a fan-shaped like one, which is bounded by

$$\begin{cases} \left\| \left(\theta_{A1}, \theta_{A2} \right) - \left(\theta_{\min}, \frac{\pi}{2} \right) \right\|_2 \leq r_f^2 \\ \Delta\theta_{\min} \leq \theta_{A2} \leq \theta_{A1} \leq \frac{\pi}{2} \end{cases} \quad (47)$$

where r_f is the radius of the fan-shaped area. SI of different θ_{A1} and θ_{A2} is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 SI of different θ_{A1} and θ_{A2}

The area bounded by red lines satisfies Eq. (46), while the whole fan-shaped area satisfies Eq. (47). It can be seen that as the difference between θ_{A1} and θ_{A2} increases, the singularity of the mechanism decreases.

5.2 GDCI fitting using the neural network

The computation of the dynamic model and GDCI is a time-consuming process. In this paper, the neural network is used to fit the model and expedite the computation. The inputs of the neural network are θ_{A1} and θ_{A2} . Considering the strong dependency of GDCI on θ_{A1} and θ_{A2} , three-hidden-layer neural networks are built and trained to make a balance between training efficiency and accuracy. Mean Square Error (MSE) is adopted as the value for the loss function, while ADAM optimizer is used as the optimization method. Our dataset is divided into three subsets, a training set, a validation set and a testing set, which accounts for 81%, 9% and 10% of the data, respectively. All data is normalized prior to feeding into the neural network.

Due to the symmetry of the 4UPS–UPU parallel mechanism, $\text{GDCI}_1 = \text{GDCI}_2$ and $\text{GDCI}_3 = \text{GDCI}_4$. Therefore, only three neural networks are needed. After the training of neural networks, the MSE of GDCI_0 , GDCI_1 (GDCI_2) and GDCI_3 (GDCI_4) are 1.6063×10^{-4} , 4.8776×10^{-5} and 1.3549×10^{-4} , respectively, which proves the availability of using the neural network to fit GDCI. GDCI of θ_{A1} and θ_{A2} satisfying constraints given by Eq. (47) is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 GDCI of θ_{A1} and θ_{A2}

It can be seen that the coupling effects of the UPU chain is relatively small. GDCI_0 is small when the chain positions on the moving platform are close to the y axis, but GDCI_1 (GDCI_2) is large in such a circumstance. For GDCI_3 (GDCI_4), θ_{A1} is dominant for its value while θ_{A2} plays a less important role.

5.3 Chain position optimization at the moving platform

In this section, the chain positions at the moving platform are optimized to reduce dynamic coupling effects based on CDCI. To compute CDCI, it is necessary to compute the minimum of GDCI. Since Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm is computational efficient and robust to control parameters, it is used to find the minimum of CDCI and GDCI. PSO solves for the minimum by having a population of candidate solutions, i.e., dubbed particles, and moving these particles in the direction

guided by the local the global best-known positions. The number of particles is chosen to be 50, which has fast convergence and high effectiveness for searching the minima of GDCI and CDCI. The maximum iteration speed is 2. The inertia weight, cognitive coefficient and social coefficient are all set to be 1. Iteration ends when most of the particles go into convergence. By using PSO, the minimum of GDCI is found, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Minimum of GDCI and its position

Chain number	Minimum of GDCI	$\theta_{A1} / ^\circ$	$\theta_{A2} / ^\circ$
0	0.303	26.79	10.00
1 (2)	0.752	90.00	64.00
3 (4)	0.699	90.00	31.28

Therefore, CDCI of different θ_{A1} and θ_{A2} can be solved based on the result in Tab. 1. The iteration process of PSO for solving the minimum of CDCI is shown in Fig. 8. The red dots signify the dubbed particles. They are distributed randomly in the area bounded by Eq. (46) at the beginning. As iteration goes on, the particles move in the direction shown by red arrows and their color goes from light red to crimson. The blue dots and arrows show the iteration of global best solutions and a detailed view is provided in the black box. The colored background within the black box shows the value of GDCI.

Fig. 8 Iteration process for solving the minimum of CDCI

As shown in Fig. 8, CDCI reaches its minimum 0.466 when θ_{A1} is 90° and θ_{A2} is 10° , which is almost a 50% drop from its worst value of 0.906. In this circumstance, the strict restraints given by Eq. (46) are satisfied. It is also shown in Fig. 6 that SI is relatively small in such a configuration. Therefore, $\theta_{B1} = 45^\circ$, $\theta_{B2} = 45^\circ$, $\theta_{A1} = 90^\circ$ and $\theta_{A2} = 10^\circ$ are adopted as the optimized chain positions and the parallel mechanism has less singularity and weak dynamic coupling in its workspace.

6 Conclusion

This paper investigates the chain position optimization of a 4UPS–UPU parallel mechanism to mitigate its dynamic coupling effects. By considering the maximum moving range of both Cartesian

and joint coordinates, the Jacobian matrix is modified to make its determinant non-dimensional and scaling irrelevant. SI is then defined to judge singularity of the mechanism, facilitating the optimization of chain positions at the base platform to prevent singularity. Additionally, CDCI is proposed to quantitatively measure the dynamic coupling effects of the parallel mechanism under varying velocity and acceleration conditions. Leveraging this index, the chain positions at the moving platform are optimized by neural networks and PSO. After optimization, CDCI drops from 0.906 to 0.466. Both the singularity index and the comprehensive dynamic coupling index have clear physical interpretations and applicability to any non-redundant parallel mechanism.

Appendix

A.1 Chain position optimization at the moving platform

Table A.1 Geometric parameters of the 4UPS–UPU mechanism (Unit: m)

Parameter	Value
R	0.35
r	0.15
l_{B0}	0.25
l_{A0}	0.2

Table A.2 Inertia parameters of the 4UPS–UPU mechanism

Parameter (Unit)	Value
m_A (kg)	5.584
m_{B0} (kg)	2.792
m_{A0} (kg)	3.971
ρ_{Bi} (kg/m ³)	7.9×10^3
ρ_{Ai} (kg/m ³)	7.9×10^3
I'_A (kg·m ²)	diag(0.0628 0.0314 0.0314)
I'_{B0} (kg·m ²)	diag(0.0057 0.0610 0.0610)
I'_{A0} (kg·m ²)	diag(0.0032 0.0545 0.0545)

A.2 Expression of $\dot{\mathbf{J}}_{oi}$

$$\dot{\mathbf{J}}_{oi} = \left\{ \frac{1}{\kappa_i} \begin{bmatrix} w_{iz}s\gamma_i c\gamma_i & -w_{iz}s^2\gamma_i & (w_{iy}s\gamma_i - w_{ix}c\gamma_i)s\gamma_i \\ w_{iz}c^2\gamma_i & -w_{iz}s\gamma_i c\gamma_i & (w_{iy}s\gamma_i - w_{ix}c\gamma_i)c\gamma_i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{\lambda_i} \begin{bmatrix} s\gamma_i c\gamma_i c\varphi_i & c^2\gamma_i c\varphi_i & 0 \\ -s^2\gamma_i c\varphi_i & -s\gamma_i c\gamma_i c\varphi_i & 0 \\ -s\gamma_i s\varphi_i & -c\gamma_i s\varphi_i & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{wi}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{oi}}{\partial \dot{P}_j} = \left\{ \frac{1}{\kappa_i} \begin{bmatrix} w_{iz} s \gamma_i c \gamma_i & -w_{iz} s^2 \gamma_i & (w_{iy} s \gamma_i - w_{ix} c \gamma_i) s \gamma_i \\ w_{iz} c^2 \gamma_i & -w_{iz} s \gamma_i c \gamma_i & (w_{iy} s \gamma_i - w_{ix} c \gamma_i) c \gamma_i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{\lambda_i} \begin{bmatrix} s \gamma_i c \gamma_i c \varphi_i & c^2 \gamma_i c \varphi_i & 0 \\ -s^2 \gamma_i c \varphi_i & -s \gamma_i c \gamma_i c \varphi_i & 0 \\ -s \gamma_i s \varphi_i & -c \gamma_i s \varphi_i & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \frac{\partial \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{wi}}{\partial \dot{P}_j} \\ + \left\{ \frac{1}{\kappa_i} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{e}_3^T \mathbf{J}_{wi} \mathbf{e}_j s \gamma_i c \gamma_i & -\mathbf{e}_3^T \mathbf{J}_{wi} \mathbf{e}_j s^2 \gamma_i & \mathbf{e}_2^T \mathbf{J}_{wi} \mathbf{e}_j s^2 \gamma_i - \mathbf{e}_1^T \mathbf{J}_{wi} \mathbf{e}_j s \gamma_i c \gamma_i \\ \mathbf{e}_3^T \mathbf{J}_{wi} \mathbf{e}_j c^2 \gamma_i & -\mathbf{e}_3^T \mathbf{J}_{wi} \mathbf{e}_j s \gamma_i c \gamma_i & \mathbf{e}_2^T \mathbf{J}_{wi} \mathbf{e}_j s \gamma_i c \gamma_i - \mathbf{e}_1^T \mathbf{J}_{wi} \mathbf{e}_j c^2 \gamma_i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{\kappa_i^2} \begin{bmatrix} 2(w_{iy} s \gamma_i - w_{ix} c \gamma_i) c \gamma_i & 2(w_{ix} c \gamma_i - w_{iy} s \gamma_i) c \gamma_i & -2w_{iz} \\ \mathbf{J}_{wi} \mathbf{e}_j \begin{bmatrix} w_{iz} s \gamma_i c \gamma_i & -w_{iz} s^2 \gamma_i & (w_{iy} s \gamma_i - w_{ix} c \gamma_i) s \gamma_i \\ w_{iz} c^2 \gamma_i & -w_{iz} s \gamma_i c \gamma_i & (w_{iy} s \gamma_i - w_{ix} c \gamma_i) c \gamma_i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ + \frac{1}{\lambda_i \kappa_i} \begin{bmatrix} w_{iz} c \varphi_i & -w_{iz} s \varphi_i & w_{iy} s \varphi_i - w_{ix} c \varphi_i \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{J}_{wi} \mathbf{e}_j \begin{bmatrix} -s \gamma_i c \gamma_i s \varphi_i & -c^2 \gamma_i s \varphi_i & 0 \\ s^2 \gamma_i s \varphi_i & s \gamma_i c \gamma_i s \varphi_i & 0 \\ -s \gamma_i c \varphi_i & -c \gamma_i c \varphi_i & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ + \frac{w_{ix} s \gamma_i + w_{iy} c \gamma_i}{\lambda_i^3} \begin{bmatrix} s \gamma_i & c \gamma_i & 0 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{J}_{wi} \mathbf{e}_j \begin{bmatrix} s \gamma_i c \gamma_i c \varphi_i & c^2 \gamma_i c \varphi_i & 0 \\ -s^2 \gamma_i c \varphi_i & -s \gamma_i c \gamma_i c \varphi_i & 0 \\ -s \gamma_i s \varphi_i & -c \gamma_i s \varphi_i & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \mathbf{J}_{wi},$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{vBi}}{\partial \dot{P}_j} = \left\{ (\mathbf{e}_j^T \mathbf{J}_{oi}^T \mathbf{w}_i \mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{w}_i \mathbf{e}_j^T \mathbf{J}_{oi}^T) \mathbf{J}_{oi} - [\mathbf{w}_i \times] \tilde{\mathbf{I}}_j \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{oi} \right\} r_{CBi} \quad \text{and}$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{vAi}}{\partial \dot{P}_j} = \left\{ (\mathbf{e}_j^T \mathbf{J}_{oi}^T \mathbf{w}_i \mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{w}_i \mathbf{e}_j^T \mathbf{J}_{oi}^T) \mathbf{J}_{oi} - [\mathbf{w}_i \times] \tilde{\mathbf{I}}_j \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{oi} \right\} r_{CAi} + \mathbf{w}_i \frac{\partial (\mathbf{e}_i^T \dot{\mathbf{J}})}{\partial \dot{P}_j};$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{wi}}{\partial \dot{P}_j} = \left\{ \tilde{\mathbf{I}}_j \dot{\mathbf{J}}_v - [(\tilde{\mathbf{I}}_j \tilde{\mathbf{J}}_{\omega P} \mathbf{a}_i) \times] \mathbf{J}_{\omega} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{w}_i \mathbf{w}_i^T) - (\mathbf{J}_v - [\mathbf{a}_i \times] \mathbf{J}_{\omega}) (\mathbf{J}_{wi} \mathbf{e}_j \mathbf{w}_i^T + \mathbf{w}_i \mathbf{e}_j^T \mathbf{J}_{wi}^T) - \mathbf{e}_i^T \mathbf{J} \mathbf{e}_j \mathbf{J}_{wi} \right\} / q_i,$$

$$\frac{\partial (\mathbf{e}_i^T \dot{\mathbf{J}})}{\partial \dot{P}_j} = \mathbf{w}_i^T \left(\tilde{\mathbf{I}}_j \dot{\mathbf{J}}_v + q_i [(\mathbf{J}_{oi} \mathbf{e}_j) \times] [\mathbf{w}_i \times] \mathbf{J}_{oi} - \mathbf{a}_i \tilde{\mathbf{I}}_j \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{\omega} - [(\mathbf{J}_{\omega} \mathbf{e}_j) \times] [\mathbf{a}_i \times] \mathbf{J}_{\omega} \right) - \mathbf{e}_i^T \mathbf{J} \mathbf{e}_j [\mathbf{w}_i \times] \mathbf{J}_{oi};$$

$\tilde{\mathbf{I}}_j = [\mathbf{O}_{3 \times 3} \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{I}_3 \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{O}_{3 \times 3}]$, in which $\tilde{\mathbf{I}}_j$ can be divided into 5 submatrices with the j th submatrix

being \mathbf{I}_3 and others being $\mathbf{O}_{3 \times 3}$. Based on Eq. (A.1), \mathbf{C} can be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{C} = \sum_{j=1}^{23} \mathbf{Q}_j \dot{P}_j \mathbf{S}_j \dot{P}_j \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where $\mathbf{Q}_1 = m_A \mathbf{J}^{-T} \mathbf{J}_v^T$, $\mathbf{Q}_2 = \mathbf{J}^{-T} \mathbf{J}_{\omega}^T \mathbf{I}_A$, $\mathbf{Q}_3 = \mathbf{J}^{-T} \mathbf{J}_{\omega}^T$, $\mathbf{Q}_{i+4} = m_{Bi} \mathbf{J}^{-T} \mathbf{J}_{vBi}^T$, $\mathbf{Q}_{i+9} = \mathbf{J}^{-T} \mathbf{J}_{oi}^T (\mathbf{I}_{Bi} + \mathbf{I}_{Ai})$,

$\mathbf{Q}_{i+14} = \mathbf{J}^{-T} \mathbf{J}_{oi}^T$, $\mathbf{Q}_{i+19} = m_{Ai} \mathbf{J}^{-T} \mathbf{J}_{vAi}^T$, $\mathbf{S}_1 = \dot{\mathbf{J}}_v$, $\mathbf{S}_2 = \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{\omega}$, $\mathbf{S}_3 = \tilde{\mathbf{J}}_{\omega P} \mathbf{I}_A \mathbf{J}_{\omega}$, $\mathbf{S}_{i+4} = \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{vBi}$, $\mathbf{S}_{i+9} = \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{oi}$,

$\mathbf{S}_{i+14} = \tilde{\mathbf{J}}_{\omega P} (\mathbf{I}_{Bi} + \mathbf{I}_{Ai}) \mathbf{J}_{oi}$ and $\mathbf{S}_{i+19} = \dot{\mathbf{J}}_{vAi}$; $i = 0, \dots, 4$. Therefore, the centrifugal term in the dynamic

equation of the i th chain is

$$C_i = \dot{\mathbf{P}}^T \mathbf{H}_i(\mathbf{P}) \dot{\mathbf{P}} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where $H_{i(j,k)} = \sum_{n=1}^{23} \sum_{m=1}^3 \mathbf{e}_i^T \mathbf{Q}_n \mathbf{e}_m \mathbf{e}_{m+3j-3}^T \mathbf{S}_n \mathbf{e}_k \cdot H_{i(j,k)}$ means the element at the j th row and the k th column of matrix \mathbf{H}_i .

References

1. Tian HB, Ma HW, Xia J, et al. Stiffness Analysis of a Metamorphic Parallel Mechanism with Three Configurations. *Mechanism and Machine Theory* 2019; 142. DOI: 10.1016/j.mechmachtheory.2019.103595.
2. Wu J, Yu G, Gao Y and Wang L. Mechatronics modeling and vibration analysis of a 2-DOF parallel manipulator in a 5-DOF hybrid machine tool. *Mechanism and Machine Theory* 2018; 121: 1339-1351. Article. DOI: 10.1016/j.mechmachtheory.2017.10.023.
3. Wu J, Wang J, Wang L and Li T. Dynamics and control of a planar 3-DOF parallel manipulator with actuation redundancy. *Mechanism and Machine Theory* 2009; 44: 835-849. Article. DOI: 10.1016/j.mechmachtheory.2008.04.002.
4. Lee M, Kim J, Hyung S, et al. A Compact Ankle Exoskeleton With a Multiaxis Parallel Linkage Mechanism. *IEEE-ASME Transactions on Mechatronics* 2021; 26: 191-202. DOI: 10.1109/tmech.2020.3008372.
5. Liu YX, Zhao JY, Yao YG, et al. High-speed parallel robot dynamic modelling based on PLC. *Journal of Supercomputing* 2020; 76: 3158-3172. DOI: 10.1007/s11227-018-2530-3.
6. Wu J, Wang XJ, Zhang BB and Huang T. Multi-Objective Optimal Design of a Novel 6-DOF Spray-Painting Robot. *Robotica* 2021; 39: 2268-2282. DOI: 10.1017/s026357472100031x.
7. Song Y, Wu J, Liu Z, et al. Similitude Analysis Method of the Dynamics of a Hybrid Spray-Painting Robot Considering Electromechanical Coupling Effect. *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics* 2021; 26: 2986-2997. Article. DOI: 10.1109/TMECH.2021.3049388.
8. Zarkandi S. Dynamic Modeling and Power Optimization of a 4RPSP+PS Parallel Flight Simulator Machine. *Robotica* 2022; 40: 646-671. DOI: 10.1017/s0263574721000746.
9. Xu YD, Chen Y, Liu WL, et al. Degree of Freedom and Dynamic Analysis of the Multi-Loop Coupled Passive-Input Overconstrained Deployable Tetrahedral Mechanisms for Truss Antennas. *Journal of Mechanisms and Robotics-Transactions of the Asme* 2020; 12. DOI: 10.1115/1.4044729.
10. Cha SW, Kang SR, Hwang YH, et al. Design and control of a parallel mechanism haptic master for robot surgery using magneto-rheological clutches and brakes. *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures* 2018; 29: 3829-3844. DOI: 10.1177/1045389x18799477.
11. Zhang J, Gao F, Yu H and Zhao X. Use of an orthogonal parallel robot with redundant actuation as an earthquake simulator and its experiments. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers Part C-Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science* 2012; 226: 257-272. DOI: 10.1177/0954406211413050.
12. Yang JF, Xu ZB, Wu QW, et al. Dynamic modeling and control of a 6-DOF micro-vibration simulator. *Mechanism and Machine Theory* 2016; 104: 350-369. DOI: 10.1016/j.mechmachtheory.2016.06.011.
13. Aimedee F, Gogu G, Dai JS, et al. Redundant Singularities Versus Constraint Singularities in Parallel Mechanisms. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers Part C-Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science* 2016; 230: 445-453. DOI: 10.1177/0954406215608891.
14. Lacombe J and Gosselin C. Singularity Analysis of a Kinematically Redundant (6+2)-DOF Parallel Mechanism for General Configurations. *Mechanism and Machine Theory* 2022; 176. DOI: 10.1016/j.mechmachtheory.2022.105015.
15. Qi Y and Song Y. Coupled Kinematic and Dynamic Analysis of Parallel Mechanism Flying in Space. *Mechanism*

and Machine Theory 2018; 124: 104-117. DOI: 10.1016/j.mechmachtheory.2018.02.003.

16. Liu X, Zhao TS, Luo EJ, et al. Coupling 3-PSR/PSU 5-Axis Compensation Mechanism for Stabilized Platform and its Analysis. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers Part C-Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science* 2013; 227: 1619-1629. DOI: 10.1177/0954406212460453.
17. Liu H, Huang T and Chetwynd DG. A Method to Formulate a Dimensionally Homogeneous Jacobian of Parallel Manipulators. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics* 2011; 27: 150-156. DOI: 10.1109/TRO.2010.2082091.
18. Liu HT, Huang T and Chetwynd DG. An Approach for Acceleration Analysis of Lower Mobility Parallel Manipulators. *Journal of Mechanisms and Robotics-Transactions of the Asme* 2011; 3. DOI: 10.1115/1.4003271.
19. Khan WA and Angeles J. The Kinetostatic Optimization of Robotic Manipulators: The Inverse and the Direct Problems. *Journal of Mechanical Design* 2006; 128: 168-178. DOI: 10.1115/1.2120808.
20. Wu J, Ye H, Yu G and Huang T. A Novel Dynamic Evaluation Method and its Application to a 4-DOF Parallel Manipulator. *Mechanism and Machine Theory* 2022; 168. DOI: 10.1016/j.mechmachtheory.2021.104627.
21. Kong MX, Zhang Y, Du ZJ and Sun LN. A Novel Approach to Deriving the Unit-Homogeneous Jacobian Matrices of Mechanisms. In: *IEEE International Conference on Mechatronics and Automation* Harbin, China, Aug 05-08 2007, 2007 iee international conference on mechatronics and automation, vols i-v, conference proceedings, pp.3051-3055.
22. Pond G and Carretero JA. Formulating Jacobian Matrices for the Dexterity Analysis of Parallel Manipulators. *Mechanism and Machine Theory* 2006; 41: 1505-1519. DOI: 10.1016/j.mechmachtheory.2006.01.003.
23. Zhao YQ, Mei JP, Niu WT, et al. Coupling Analysis of a 5-Degree-of-Freedom Hybrid Manipulator Based on a Global Index. *Science Progress* 2020; 103. DOI: 10.1177/0036850419881896.
24. Ogbobe P, Hongzhou J, Jingfeng H, et al. Analysis of Coupling Effects on Hydraulic Controlled 6 Degrees of Freedom Parallel Manipulator Using Joint Space Inverse Mass Matrix. In: *2009 Second International Conference on Intelligent Computation Technology and Automation* 10-11 Oct. 2009 2009, pp.845-848.
25. Wang D, Wu J, Wang LP, et al. Research on the Dynamic Characteristics of a 3-DOF Parallel Tool Head. *Industrial Robot-the International Journal of Robotics Research and Application* 2017; 44: 28-37. DOI: 10.1108/ir-03-2016-0094.